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**Report on feasibility and acceptance the catalyst
platform**

Submission of Deliverable

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1 Introduction

The idea of the catalyst platform:

One of the goals of EU-PolarNet 2 is to develop cooperation tools to strengthen European Polar coordination and to facilitate interaction among national Polar research programmes in Europe. One of the main cooperation tools is the Catalyst Platform that shall improve the information flow within the European Polar community. The Catalyst Platform accommodates a continuous information exchange and an interactive room as a discussion forum for the Polar community to identify synergies and develop partnerships within Europe.

The Platform will serve as the core of the European Polar Coordination Office (EPCO) which will be one of the main outcomes of EU-PolarNet-2 and will secure that its legacy is well preserved. The Platform is intended to provide all important information on European polar research and serve as an important coordination asset for the European Polar community. It will also contain a significant part of the outcome generated by the European Polar Cluster projects, securing the legacy of EU-funded European Polar Research. It shall become the central database and exchange service of the European Polar Community. The Catalyst Platform is expected to serve also as a catalyser where researchers, stake- and rightholders, industry, and others discuss new ideas and big collaborative initiatives involving several parties.

The Catalyst Platform is divided into the following sections: Resources, News, Events, Research groups, Infrastructure offers, Jobs and Discussion. In addition, the access to the recorded webinars and relevant minutes from the EU Polar Cluster task group meetings will be also incorporated. The relevant information on polar issues in Europe and in the world will also be disseminated to the community through this platform, which also will be paramount in the introduction of the main research groups.

2 The development of the tool

An open committee within EU-PolarNet-2 was created including members of different countries and EU-PolarNet 2 partners. This committee met three times conceptualising the platform from a practical point of view and preparing a list of technical requirements.

Then, the Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI) opened a public procurement procedure for the technical development of the platform and chose the company Bluelobster (now feez.ee). Bluelobster offered the best value for money and their expertise with other European initiatives (e.g. POLARDEX) represented an additional benefit. This company worked in close contact with a small group of EU-PolarNet 2 members to define the platform and check the potentiality and functionality of the different utilities. The development of the platform has gone through several rounds of refinement.

A training session, open to the EU-PolarNet-2 community, was held by Bluelobster to explain the administrator and moderator roles and train uploading, editing and publishing information on the Catalyst Platform.

Finally, the Catalyst Platform was virtually launched on 30th June 2022 and introduced to the Polar community with presentations by Nicole Biebow, Antonio Quesada, Anneli Strobel and Andrés Barbosa (<https://eu-polarnet.eu/catalyst-launch/>). The webinar can be accessed here: <https://youtu.be/-J-1ckjzeE4>.

3 Feasibility

The Catalyst Platform can be reached by the following link <https://polarcatalyst.eu/> (figure 1)

It is structured along five tabs: Resources, News, Events, Other information (Research Groups, Infrastructures and Jobs) and Discussions.

Figure 1. Screenshot of presentation page of the Catalyst Platform

The **Resources** tab (Figure 2) includes the reference to any document of interest to the polar community such as documents resulting from European polar projects, national polar strategies, papers or web pages. Each document is identified by several tags which allow it to be easily searchable.

Figure 2. Screenshot of the Resources tab in the Catalyst Platform

The principle of the tabs is that the documents do not need to be stored in the repository but will be linked via their URL or DOI. If important documents are not stored elsewhere in a permanent repository (e.g. Research Projects webpages), those documents will be uploaded to the platform to ensure their searchability. Every document referenced in the Catalyst Platform has to include an URL or DOI and mandatorily needs to be accompanied by a metadata sheet to allow an easy, complete and comprehensive search. The documents physically stored at the platform also will require a metadata sheet. This will follow the principle of: If not findable documents do not exist.

The **News** tab (Figure 3) highlights news of interest for the polar community, such as important information related to workshops, conferences, meetings, webinars (i.e. abstract deadlines, registration deadlines), call for projects, call for papers etc.

Figure 3. Screenshot of the News tab

The **Events** tab (Figure 4) shows information related to workshops, conferences and meetings of interest to the polar community.

Figure 4a. Screenshot of the Events tab

Figure 4b, Screenshot of the Events tab

The tab **Other Information** includes three sub-tabs. One is the **Research Groups** tab (figure 5) sub-folder where European polar research groups can upload information on their objectives and activities by that creating a virtual catalog of the European research groups involved in polar research.

The sub-folder of **Infrastructure offers** shows information related availabilities of polar infrastructures offered by National Polar Programmes or research groups, promoting collaboration and cooperation in polar research.

The subtab **Jobs** (figure 7) shows the job offer from National Polar Programmes, research institutes or research groups.

Figure 7. Screenshot of tab other information, subtab jobs

The tab **Discussions** (figure 8) includes the Discussion groups. This is a unique feature and one of the most important utilities of the platform. It will be a facilitated interactive forum in which different initiatives will be discussed by invitation or in an open framework. These facilitated discussions are expected to trigger initiatives that would setup synergistic activities between several interested research groups. It is not expected to become ‘one more forum’ but a facilitated forum in which the facilitator will stimulate the discussion and support new initiatives that will allow a productive exchange of ideas and synergies.

Figure 8. Screenshot of the Discussions tab

4 Governance

The governance of the Catalyst Platform includes a general coordinator of the platform with an administrator role. Dr. Andrés Barbosa (MICINN) has been appointed as Platform coordinator for the implementation phase. He will retain this role until the platform is running, and all the potential problems have been identified and solved. Then, another coordinator needs to be appointed by the EU-PolarNet 2 consortium. The EU-PolarNet 2 Management Support Team and the Work Package 1 leader have administrator roles as well. They oversee supervising the good performance of the platform and the relevance of its contents.

The role of a moderator includes second level responsibility for the Platform. Moderators are persons nominated by each partner of EU-Polar Net 2 (one person per partner). They are responsible for uploading general and institutional information of their country to the platform.

Finally, any interested member of the polar community can open discussion groups and upload specific information to these groups after signing in as a user. Several topics of wider interest will be launched as initial discussion topics by EU-PolarNet 2 facilitators to introduce the Catalyst Platform to the community. It is expected that after some months of working under directed facilitation, the discussion topics will run autonomously.

5 Acceptance by the Polar Community

The EU-PolarNet-2 and EU Polar Cluster community is eager to use the platform and utilise it for discussions and document sharing. However, we will do the first audit regarding the acceptance of the discussion forum and the repository after a period of six months in January 2023. Currently, we are preparing an outreach campaign to advertise Catalyst Platform to the community. Further tools are developed to increase the acceptance and the utilisation of the platform by the community. The goal is to make the usage of the platform beneficial for the Polar community and to encourage the community to interacting with the platform.

The European Polar Board (EPB) identified the Catalyst Platform as the crucial tool to develop the EPCO at its last plenary. All EPB members were induced to use the platform. It was presented as a beta version (launched after the meeting).

Since the Catalyst Platform has been officially launched in June 2022, we cannot provide quantitative data about the acceptance or the utilisation yet. The platform has been active only for some weeks and there has been not enough time to get representative data. We will gather the quantitative data about the utilization of the Catalyst Platform after one year (June 2023) and will update this deliverable accordingly.

The main indicators on how well the platform has been accepted by the Polar community that will be considered are:

- Number of visitors to the platform
 - o Unique visitors
 - o Total number of visits
- Distribution of visitors to the platform (country/affiliation)

- Number of clicks within the platform per entrance
- Searches in the resources folder
- Number of entries in the Discussions tab
- Information volume within the platform (including all tabs)

Suggested tools to improve the acceptance by the Polar community

- Make sure that information is relevant and up-to-date and in parts only available via the platform
- Assess the performance of the searching engine
- Use EU-PolarNet 2, EPB and EU Polar Cluster meetings to remind the EU community to use the platform
- Advertise on polar conferences and workshops
- Offer a diverse and useful content
- Make sure that discussion topics are well moderated, interesting and participative. This point will be reached by selecting appropriate moderators
- Social media campaign incl. relevant groups as SCAR, IADC, APECS